

Making a Complete Mess and Getting Away with it: Traveling Salesperson Problems with Circle Placement Variants

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Abstract—This paper explores a variation of the Traveling Salesperson Problem, where the agent places a circular obstacle next to each node once it visits it. Referred to as the Traveling Salesperson Problem with Circle Placement (TSP-CP), the aim is to maximize the obstacle radius for which a valid closed tour exists and then minimize the tour cost. The TSP-CP finds relevance in various real-world applications, such as harvesting, quarrying, and open-pit mining. We propose several novel solvers to address the TSP-CP, its variant tailored for Dubins vehicles, and a crucial subproblem known as the Traveling Salesperson Problem on self-deleting graphs (TSP-SD). Our extensive experimental results show that the proposed solvers outperform the current state-of-the-art on related problems in solution quality.

Index Terms—Task and Motion Planning, Constrained Motion Planning, Computational Geometry

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS paper addresses a variation of the Traveling Salesperson Problem (TSP), in which the agent must visit each node in a weighted graph exactly once and place a circular obstacle next to it. This problem is referred to as the Traveling Salesperson Problem with Circle Placement (TSP-CP). Similar to the TSP, the objective in the TSP-CP is to minimize the tour cost. However, TSP-CP has a different primary optimization criterion that involves maximizing the radius of the circular obstacle associated with each visited node. The TSP-CP is relevant to many real-world applications, such as autonomous harvesting [1], quarrying, and open-pit mining [2], to name only a few.

To describe the relevancy, take the open-pit mining application illustrated in Fig. 1, where the drill rig is tasked with drilling blast holes in predefined locations. The blast holes

Fig. 1. Blast hole drilling [3].

are then loaded with explosive materials in preparation for detonation. The drilling generates a pile of excess material to be placed in the vicinity of each hole. We illustrate the main criteria of the TSP-CP using this example: (1) creating a sufficiently large pile and maximizing clearance for the drill rig motion, i.e., placing the largest circles possible; (2) minimizing time and energy costs by finding the shortest tour; and (3) navigating among the obstacles created by the excess materials. This task can be modeled as an instance of the TSP-CP whose one possible solution is depicted in Fig. 2a. A similar case can be envisaged in harvesting applications when a harvester needs to deposit the largest possible amount of crops in designated areas while respecting criteria 1–3 mentioned above.

To address criteria 1–2 in the TSP-CP, we build upon the Weak Path Conforming Circle Placement Problem (WPCCP) introduced in [4]. In the WPCCP, the objective is to position the largest circles feasible on the nodes of a given tour. Unlike in the WPCCP, the tour is not given in the TSP-CP, thus enabling the placement of larger circles while simultaneously determining the optimal tour.

To account for criterion 3, i.e., navigating among circular obstacles in the TSP-CP, we employ the Travelling Salesperson Problem on self-deleting graphs (TSP-SD) formalism from [5]. In a self-deleting graph, certain edges are deleted as a result of node visitation, allowing for representing the lack of reachability in a geometric extension of the graph with obstacles.

In this paper, we propose a new problem-specific meta-heuristic solver for the TSP-SD, which outperforms the generic solver used in [5]. Then, we introduce a novel heuristic TSP-CP solver, which combines the existing algorithm for the WPCCP [4] with our newly proposed TSP-SD solver. Finally,

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we generalize the solver to accommodate the Dubins vehicle, thus introducing a new variant, the DTSP-CP¹.

II. RELATED WORK

The studied TSP-CP combines properties of several established optimization problems in various areas: Circle Packing Problems, Routing Problems, and Planning on temporal graphs. In this section, we provide an overview of these problems, describe their principal properties, and discuss their relevance to the TSP-CP.

Circle Packing Problems address the arrangement of circles in a container or a specified pattern [6]. One of the most relevant variants to the TSP-CP is the Uniform-sized Circle Packing Problem UCP2 [7], where the goal is to place a fixed number of uniform-sized, non-overlapping circles into a unit square and maximize their radius. Other variants consider arbitrary-sized packings, different shapes of the encompassing container, minimization of its size, or even general geometries of the objects to be packed [8]. However, Circle Packing Problems do not tackle the scenario where the placement is to be carried out by a vehicle. Thus, obstacle avoidance or trajectory optimization is not considered.

The trajectory planning aspect of TSP-CP is thoroughly studied in various Routing Problems, which focus on the mission and motion planning, while covering a predefined area or visiting given regions. For example, the Traveling Salesperson Problem with Neighborhoods [9] tackles the problem of finding the shortest possible tour visiting a close neighborhood of fixed target locations, such as polygons [10]. Another variant is the Close-Enough Traveling Salesperson Problem [11], where the goal is to get within a certain distance from the target location. Thus, the task corresponds to visiting a fixed-radius circle, which is very close to the goal of the TSP-CP. Both of these problems are also studied in environments with obstacles [10] [12] or with the Dubins vehicle model [13] [14], which are common choices for many robotic applications. However, unlike TSP-CP, none of these problems consider optimization of obstacle placement in time and space.

Probably the most challenging aspect of the TSP-CP is the evolution of the environment and the increasing number of obstacles over time. Formulating the TSP on temporal graphs [15], or time-evolving graphs [16], where the graph evolves in a predefined way in discrete steps, can achieve this behavior. However, these formalisms ignore that, in the TSP-CP, obstacles arise as a consequence of the agent's actions rather than being a predefined function of time. Similarly, we cannot apply solutions from the Covering Canadian Traveller Problem [17], where changes to the environment are not known in advance and unrelated to the agent's actions. A special case of the TSP-CP is studied in [18], where the vehicle is forbidden to physically pass through each node already visited. Considering the dimensions of the vehicle, this corresponds to avoiding a circular obstacle centered at a given node. Thus, the circle placement is not addressed.

The placement of circles along a given path was studied in [4] as the Weak Path Conforming Circle Placement Problem (WPCCP). In the WPCCP, circular obstacles are positioned along a TSP path to prevent collisions further along the route. However, the underlying TSP path is fixed. Additionally, the temporal aspect of the TSP-CP and tour optimization can be captured by the Traveling Salesperson Problem on self-deleting graphs (TSP-SD) [5], as the placed circular obstacles can be used to define the delete function in the TSP-SD. For these reasons, the TSP-CP problem includes the WPCCP and the TSP-SD as subproblems.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In this section, we formally define the Travelling Salesperson Problem with Circle Placement, its Dubins variant, the concept of self-deleting graphs, and the Travelling Salesperson Problem on self-deleting graphs. Fig. 2 shows solutions for instances of the TSP-CP and the DTSP-CP, using the problem formulation described in the current section.

Problem 1: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a simple, undirected, and complete Euclidean graph, where $V \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ and $|V| = n$. The *Travelling Salesperson Problem with Circle Placement (TSP-CP)* is to find a Hamiltonian cycle $c = \langle v_1, e_{1,2}, v_2, \dots, v_n, e_{n,1} \rangle$ and a set of circles $\mathcal{K} = \{\kappa_i\}_{i \in I}$, where $I = \{1, \dots, n\}$, $v_i \in V$, $e_{i,j} \in E$, κ_i is a circle with center $c_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and radius $r_i \in \mathbb{R}$, such that the following requirements are met:

- (C1) radii of all circles are equal - $\forall i \in I : r_i = r$,
- (C2) i^{th} point lies on i^{th} circle - $\forall i \in I : |v_i c_i| = r$,
- (C3) intersection of any two circles is empty - $\forall i, j \in I, i \neq j : \kappa_i \cap \kappa_j = \emptyset$,
- (C4) intersection of i^{th} circle with the rest of the cycle is empty - $\forall i \in I : \kappa_i \cap \langle e_{i,i+1}, v_{i+1}, \dots, v_n, e_{n,1} \rangle = \emptyset$,
- (O1) radius of circles r is maximal,
- (O2) given r , cycle cost $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} |e_{i,i+1}| + |e_{n,1}|$ is minimal.

The definition of the TSP-CP problem directly generalizes the Weak Path-Conforming Circles Placement Problem (WPCCP) from [4], where an input path is given and not subject to optimization. Note that (O1) criterion maximizing r is the primary objective, analogously to the WPCCP. The secondary objective (O2) then prioritizes the shorter among two solutions, given that the r is equal. In addition, the TSP-CP can be easily reformulated for the Dubins vehicle model.

Problem 2: Let $V \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be a set of points, $|V| = n$, $r_{dub} \in \mathbb{R}$. The *Dubins Travelling Salesperson Problem with Circle Placement (DTSP-CP)* is to find a Hamiltonian cycle $c = \langle v_1, \theta_1, e_{1,2}, v_2, \theta_2, \dots, v_n, \theta_n, e_{n,1} \rangle$ and a set of circles $\mathcal{K} = \{\kappa_i\}_{i \in I}$, where $I = \{1, \dots, n\}$, $v_i \in V$, $\theta_i \in [0, 2\pi)$ is angular heading from v_i , $e_{i,j}$ is the shortest Dubins maneuver from (v_i, θ_i) to (v_j, θ_j) with turning radius r_{dub} , and κ_i is a circle with center $c_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and radius $r_i \in \mathbb{R}$. The constraints and optimality criteria are identical with Problem 1.

Finally, let us define self-deleting graphs and the Traveling Salesperson Problem on self-deleting graphs (TSP-SD). The definitions are adopted from [5].

Definition 1: A *self-deleting graph* S is a tuple $S = (G, f)$ where $G = (V, E)$ is a simple, directed graph and $f : V \rightarrow 2^E$ is a *delete function*. If a vertex v is *processed*, edges $f(v)$

¹All source codes are available at <https://gitlab.ciirc.cvut.cz/imr/TSPSD/>

Fig. 3. Local search operators for the TSP-SD.

individual operators. Fig. 3 shows the solution before and after applying each operator for a given pair of indices i, j . The moved or inverted solution parts are highlighted in color.

The operators are designed so that both the validity of the solution and the cost are evaluated incrementally. This significantly enhances the scalability of the proposed solver. If an operator is applicable for all pairs of indices $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, then a naively implemented exhaustive search of the corresponding neighborhood has a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$, $\mathcal{O}(n^3 f(p))$ in case of cost and validity evaluation, respectively. Here, $f(p) = \sum_{i=1}^n f(p_i)/n$ is the average number of deleted edges per node. When evaluated incrementally, the complexities can be reduced to $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ and $\mathcal{O}(n^2 f(p))$.

3) *2-opt*: The 2-opt operator (Fig. 3a) is described in Alg. 2. Given indices i, j , 2-opt inverts a subsequence $x = \langle p_i, \dots, p_j \rangle$ of a cycle $c = \langle p_1, \dots, p_n \rangle$. The operator iterates over all pairs of indices i, j and applies the first improving pair found. Let us define the set of nodes in x as $X = \{p_i, \dots, p_j\}$, the set of nodes before x as $A = \{p_1, \dots, p_{i-1}\}$, and the set of newly added edges in inverted x as $E_X = \{e_{j,j-1}, \dots, e_{i+1,i}\}$. Then, let E_{XA} contain edges that are in E_X , but are not in the residual graph G_A - newly added edges deleted by some of the nodes in A . Finally, we can formulate several rules for the 2-opt-modified cycle $c_{cand} = \langle p_1, \dots, p_j, \dots, p_i, \dots, p_n \rangle$ to be f -conforming:

- (i) X must not delete edges in E_X - incrementally checked for edge $e_{i+1,i}$ at line 5 of Alg. 2.
- (ii) A must not delete edges in E_X - currently added $e_{i+1,i}$ is checked at line 7, previously deleted edges are stored in E_{XA} (line 12) and checked at line 8. As A becomes smaller (line 4), E_{XA} must be updated (line 6).
- (iii) $e_{i-1,j}$ must not be deleted by A (line 8).
- (iv) $e_{i,j+1}$ must not be deleted by X and A (line 8).

If all rules are satisfied, $cost(c_{cand})$ can be evaluated in constant time (line 9). If the move is improving, the current c_{cand} is returned (line 10). Otherwise, the original c is returned after testing all pairs of i, j (line 15).

4) *Move*: The move operator (Fig. 3b) attempts to move a subsequence $x = \langle p_i, \dots, p_{i+m-1} \rangle$ of fixed length m , starting at index i , to a better position j in cycle $c = \langle p_1, \dots, p_n \rangle$. Alg. 3 describes one branch of the operator - move-right, where x is moved only to the right from i . The second branch functions analogously. Let X the set of nodes in x , E_X the edges in x , and A the set of nodes in c before x (lines 2-3). Then, B is the set of nodes between x and j (line 6). For each tested combination of i, j , the following three conditions must be satisfied for the new edges in

Algorithm 2 2-opt

in: $S = (G, f)$, Ham. cycle $c = \langle p_1, \dots, p_n \rangle$ on S

- 1: **for** $j = n - 1$ to 3 **do**
- 2: $X = \{p_j\}, E_{XA} = \{\}$
- 3: **for** $i = j - 1$ to 2 **do**
- 4: $A = \{p_1, \dots, p_{i-1}\}$
- 5: **if** $e_{i+1,i} \in G_X$
- 6: $X = X \cup \{p_i\}, E_{XA} = E_{XA} \setminus G_A$
- 7: **if** $e_{i+1,i} \in G_A$
- 8: **if** $e_{i-1,j} \in G_A \wedge e_{i,j+1} \in G_{A \cup X} \wedge |E_{XA}| = 0$
- 9: **if** $eval_{2-opt}(c, i, j) < cost(c)$
- 10: **return** `apply_two_opt`(c, i, j)
- 11: **else**
- 12: $E_{XA} = E_{XA} \cup e_{i+1,i}$
- 13: **else**
- 14: **break**
- 15: **return** unchanged cycle c

Algorithm 3 move-right

in: $S = (G, f)$, $c = \langle p_1, \dots, p_n \rangle$, moved seq. length m

- 1: **for** $i = 2$ to $n - m - 1$ **do**
- 2: $A = \{p_1, \dots, p_{i-1}\}, X = \{p_i, \dots, p_{i+m-1}\}$
- 3: $E_X = \{e_{i,i+1}, \dots, e_{i+m-2,i+m-1}\}$
- 4: **if** $e_{i-1,i+m} \in G_A$
- 5: **for** $j = i + m$ to $n - 1$ **do**
- 6: $B = \{p_{i+m}, \dots, p_j\}$
- 7: **if** $E_X \not\subset G_B$
- 8: **break**
- 9: **if** $e_{j,i} \in G_{A \cup B} \wedge e_{i+m-1,j+1} \in G_{A \cup B \cup X}$
- 10: **if** $eval_{mr}(c, i, j, m) < cost(c)$
- 11: **return** `apply_move_right`(c, i, j, m)
- 12: **return** unchanged cycle c

$c_{cand} = \langle p_1, \dots, p_{i-1}, p_{i+m}, \dots, p_j, p_i, \dots, p_{i+m-1}, p_{j+1}, \dots, p_n \rangle$:

- (i) $e_{i-1,i+m}$ must not be deleted by A (line 4),
- (ii) $e_{j,i}$ must not be deleted by A, B (line 9),
- (iii) $e_{i+m-1,j+1}$ must not be deleted by A, B, X (line 9), plus one for those edges that were moved right:
- (iv) E_X must not be deleted by B (line 7).

When (i)-(iv) are satisfied, the cost of c_{cand} is evaluated in constant time. If an improving move is found, it is applied and returned. Otherwise, c remains unchanged (line 10-12).

5) *Swap*: The swap operator (Fig. 3c), described in Alg. 4, attempts to swap two subsequences $x = \langle p_i, \dots, p_{i+k-1} \rangle, y = \langle p_j, \dots, p_{j+l-1} \rangle$ of fixed lengths k, l . Assuming $i < j$, the operator is not symmetric, thus `swap-asym`(S, c, k, l) and `swap-asym`(S, c, l, k) must both be run if $k \neq l$. Note that the swap operator cannot be replaced by running the move operator sequentially with parameters k, l , as the intermediate solution may be infeasible due to the delete function f . Let us denote the set of nodes in c before x as $A = \{p_1, \dots, p_{i-1}\}$, nodes in x as X , nodes between x and y as $B = \{p_{i+k}, \dots, p_{j-1}\}$ and nodes in y as Y (line 4). If $i + k = j, B = \emptyset$. For each tested combination of i, j , the following six conditions must be satisfied so that $c_{cand} = \langle p_1, \dots, p_j, \dots, p_{j+l-1}, \dots, p_i, \dots, p_{i+k-1}, \dots, p_n \rangle$ is f -conforming:

Algorithm 4 swap-asym

```

in:  $S = (G, f)$ ,  $c = \langle p_1, \dots, p_n \rangle$ , swapped seq. lengths  $k, l$ 
1: for  $j = n - l$  to  $k + 2$  do
2:    $Y = \{p_j, \dots, p_{j+l-1}\}$ 
3:   for  $i = j - k$  to  $2$  do
4:      $A = \{p_1, \dots, p_{i-1}\}$ ,  $X = \{p_i, \dots, p_{i+k-1}\}$ ,  $B =$ 
        $\{p_{i+k}, \dots, p_{j-1}\}$ ,  $E_X = \{e_{i,i+1}, \dots, e_{i+k-2,i+k-1}\}$ 
5:      $e_1 = e_{i-1,j}$ ,  $e_4 = e_{i+k-1,j+l}$ 
6:     if  $E_B \not\subset G_Y$ 
7:       break
8:     if  $i + k = j$ 
9:        $e_2 = e_3 = e_{j+l-1,i}$ 
10:    else
11:       $e_2 = e_{j+l-1,i+k}$ ,  $e_3 = e_{j-1,i}$ 
12:      if  $e_1 \in G_A \wedge e_2 \in G_{A \cup Y} \wedge e_3 \in G_{A \cup Y \cup B} \wedge e_4 \in$ 
         $G_{A \cup Y \cup B \cup X} \wedge E_X \subset G_B \wedge E_X \subset G_Y$ 
13:        if  $\text{eval}_{\text{sa}}(c, i, j, k, l)$ 
14:          return  $\text{apply\_swap\_asym}(c, i, j, k, l)$ 
15:    return unchanged  $c$ 

```

(i) nodes in Y are shifted to the left, so they must not delete edges E_B in B (line 6).

All newly added edges must not be deleted (line 12):

(ii) $e_1 = e_{i-1,j}$ by A , (iii) e_2 by A, Y , (iv) e_3 by A, Y, B ,

(v) $e_4 = e_{i+k-1,j+l}$ by A, Y, B, X .

(vi) edges E_X in x are shifted to the right, so they must not be deleted by B (line 12). If $B = \emptyset$, $e_2 = e_3$. If all conditions are met, $\text{cost}(c_{\text{cand}})$ can be evaluated in constant time. If an improving move is found, it is applied and returned (line 14).

B. TSP-CP solver - fixed radius

The proposed solver for the TSP-CP with a fixed radius is described in Alg. 5. The input is a Euclidean graph $G = (V, E)$, a radius r and a TSP cycle c_{TSP} . If the instance is feasible, the output is a valid TSP-CP Hamiltonian cycle and a set of circles \mathcal{K} of the given radius r . First, a placement of circles \mathcal{K} along c_{TSP} is found using the Local search algorithm for a relaxed problem: the WPCCP with fixed radius [4] (line 1). For each node $v_i \in c_{TSP}$, $c_{TSP} = \langle v_1, e_{1,2}, \dots, v_n, e_{n,1} \rangle$, this algorithm samples a set of candidate circles κ_i^c , discards those candidate circles that are in collision with the rest of the cycle $\langle v_i, e_{i,i+1}, \dots, v_n, e_{n,1} \rangle$ and then finds a least-colliding placement \mathcal{K} using a simple local optimization procedure. Here, the algorithm is configured to treat collisions between the edges of the cycle and the circles as a penalized soft constraint. Collisions between the circles themselves are not allowed. If the algorithm returns a circle placement \mathcal{K} , it is guaranteed to respect constraints (C1), (C2) and (C3) of Problem 1. The constraint (C4) may not be satisfied. If it is, c_{TSP} and \mathcal{K} represent a valid solution to the TSP-CP with a fixed radius and are returned (line 3). The $\text{cost}(c_{TSP})$ is optimal for TSP-CP if it is optimal for TSP. Both problems are solved on the same graph G , but some edges may be removed in the TSP-CP. Thus, the optimal TSP-CP solution cannot be better than the TSP one.

Otherwise, \mathcal{K} satisfies (C1), (C2), and (C3), but the initial c_{TSP} violates (C4), as illustrated in Fig. 2c. Then, a TSP-

Algorithm 5 TSP-CP solver - fixed radius

```

in: Euclidean graph  $G$ , radius  $r$ , TSP cycle  $c_{TSP}$ 
1:  $\mathcal{K} = \text{place\_circles\_soft}(c_{TSP}, r)$ 
2: if  $\text{is\_valid\_TSPCP}(c_{TSP}, \mathcal{K})$ 
3:   return  $c_{TSP}, \mathcal{K}$ 
4: else if  $\mathcal{K} \neq \emptyset$ 
5:    $f = \text{generate\_TSPSD}(G, \mathcal{K})$ 
6:    $c_{TSPSD} = \text{GRASP}(G, f, c_{TSP})$ 
7:   if  $c_{TSPSD} \neq \emptyset$ 
8:     return TSP-CP cycle  $c_{TSPSD}$ , circles  $\mathcal{K}$ 
9:   else
10:    return  $\emptyset$ 

```

SD instance is generated for $G = (V, E)$ and \mathcal{K} (line 5) in the following fashion: $\forall e_i \in E, v_j \in V : f(v_j) \leftarrow f(v_j) \cup e_i \iff k_j \cap e_i \neq \emptyset$. In other words, an edge e_i is added to the delete function $f(v_j)$, if e_i intersects the circle $k_j \in \mathcal{K}$ corresponding to the node v_j . The resulting TSP-SD instance $S = (G, f)$ is then solved using the proposed TSP-SD GRASP solver (line 6). In this phase, the circle placement \mathcal{K} is fixed, and the TSP-SD solver attempts to rearrange the cycle c_{TSP} to satisfy (C4) and minimize (O2) to a local optimum. If it succeeds, the resulting c_{TSPSD} is a valid TSP-CP cycle. The TSP-SD solver uses an exact construction procedure, which is run 20 times with a time limit of 20 seconds. If it fails to find a valid initial solution, the TSP-SD subproblem is considered infeasible.

C. TSP-CP solver

The proposed approach to solve the TSP-CP is presented in Alg. 6. The input to the algorithm is a Euclidean graph $G = (V, E)$, and the output is a placement of circles \mathcal{K} of maximum radius r and an f -conforming TSP-CP Hamiltonian cycle c of minimal length. First, the optimal TSP solution c_{TSP} for G is found using the exact Concorde TSP solver [22] (line 1). Then the Interval Bisection Algorithm for the Weak Path Conforming Circles Placement Problem (WPCCP) from [4] is run, given c_{TSP} (line 2). This algorithm guarantees finding a placement \mathcal{K} , that satisfies all constraints (C1) to (C4) and maximizes the radius r (criterion (O1)), given a fixed cycle c_{TSP} . It also returns the upper bound estimate ub for r . However, the radius r can be further increased if we relax the WPCCP to the TSP-CP and allow the input cycle c_{TSP} to change. For this purpose, the bisection algorithm is adapted for the TSP-CP in the rest of Alg. 6 (lines 4-10). The initial interval is given by ub and r from the previous step. In each loop of the interval bisection, a new target radius $r_{\text{cand}} > r$ is calculated (line 5). Then, given G, r_{cand} and c_{TSP} , the TSP-CP solver for fixed radius is run in an attempt to find a new f -conforming TSP-CP cycle c_{cand} and new circle placement $\mathcal{K}_{\text{cand}}$ (line 6). According to the result, the bounds lb, ub are adjusted (lines 7-10). The algorithm terminates once the bounds difference $ub - lb$ is within a predefined limit $\epsilon = 0.1$ (line 4) and returns the best values of c, \mathcal{K} and r (line 11).

Algorithm 6 TSP-CP solver

in: Euclidean graph G

- 1: $c_{TSP} = \text{solve_TSP}(G)$
- 2: $\mathcal{K}, r, ub = \text{interval_bisection}(c_{TSP})$
- 3: $lb = r, c = c_{TSP}$
- 4: **while** $ub - lb > \epsilon$ **do**
- 5: $r_{cand} = \frac{lb+ub}{2}$
- 6: $c_{cand}, \mathcal{K}_{cand} = \text{TSPCP_fixed_r}(G, r_{cand}, c_{TSP})$
- 7: **if** $c_{cand} \neq \emptyset$
- 8: $lb = r_{cand}, c = c_{cand}, K = \mathcal{K}_{cand}, r = r_{cand}$
- 9: **else**
- 10: $ub = r_{cand}$
- 11: **return** TSP-CP cycle c , circles \mathcal{K} , radius r

D. Dubins TSP-CP solver

The proposed approach for the DTSP-CP directly adapts the TSP-CP solvers described in Alg. 5 and 6 to the Dubins vehicle model [23]. The Dubins variant is principally identical to the Euclid variant. However, several components need to be replaced or adjusted. All necessary changes are discussed in this section and marked in blue in Alg. 5 and 6. A Dubins maneuver is given by a pair of configurations (x, y, θ) and a turning radius r_{dub} , where $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^2$ are the coordinates of the maneuver endpoints, $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$ are angular headings at each endpoint. We only consider the shortest maneuver, which is unique [23].

The first modification is needed on line 5 of Alg. 5, where a TSP-SD instance is generated, given graph G and circle placement \mathcal{K} . Instead of using the Euclidean graph $G = (V, E)$ as input, a graph $G_{dub} = (V_{dub}, E_{dub})$ is created, based on the cycle $c_{DTSP} = \langle v_1, \theta_1, e_{1,2}, \dots, v_n, \theta_n, e_{n,1} \rangle$, which is a DTSP solution on G . The nodes are defined as $V_{dub} = \{v_i \in c_{DTSP}\}$, where $v_i = (x_i, y_i, \theta_i)$. In other words, the headings θ are part of the node coordinates and taken from c_{DTSP} . Therefore, the headings are fixed in V_{dub} . The edges E_{dub} are then simply the shortest Dubins maneuvers between all pairs of nodes in V_{dub} , and the TSP-SD delete function f is given by collisions between circles $\kappa_i \in \mathcal{K}$ and Dubins maneuvers in E_{dub} .

The second modification is required on line 1 of Alg. 6, where we generate the initial DTSP cycle c_{DTSP} . It corresponds to the need to select an appropriate heading θ_i in each node. This is achieved by transforming the problem into the Generalized Traveling Salesperson Problem (GTSP), where the goal is to plan the shortest cycle possible, visiting exactly one element from each set V_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Here, $V_i = \{(v_i, \theta_1), \dots, (v_i, \theta_k)\}$, where the headings θ_j , $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ are uniformly sampled for each $v \in V$. This subproblem is solved using the Generalized Large Neighborhood Search (GLNS) [24] metaheuristic solver for the GTSP.

The third modification is required on line 1 of Alg. 5, where the Local search algorithm for the WPCCP [4] is used to find a circle placement \mathcal{K} , given cycle c_{TSP} . For each node $v_i \in c_{TSP}$, $c_{TSP} = \langle v_1, e_{1,2}, \dots, v_n, e_{n,1} \rangle$, this algorithm samples a set of candidate circles κ_i^c , penalizes or discards those candidate circles that are in collision with the rest of

the cycle $\langle v_i, e_{i,i+1}, \dots, v_n, e_{n,1} \rangle$ and then finds a least-colliding placement \mathcal{K} . The only difference in the Dubins variant is that collisions must be checked between Dubins maneuvers in c_{DTSP} and circles κ_i^c , which can be easily added to the implementation. The same Local search algorithm is then used within the Interval Bisection Algorithm for the WCCP [4], used in line 2 of Alg. 6, where the colliding candidate circles κ_i^c are discarded.

V. EXPERIMENTS

All proposed algorithms are experimentally evaluated. First, the GRASP solver for the TSP-SD is benchmarked against the generic solver employed in [5]. Second, the TSP-CP solver is compared with the WPCCP solver from [4]. Finally, the behavior of the DTSP-CP solver variant is studied on a small dataset for several different Dubins turning radii and compared with the TSP-CP solutions. All experiments were carried out on a dedicated machine with Ubuntu 18.04, Intel Core i7-7700, including those from [4], [5]. The gap values presented are calculated as $gap = 100(\frac{score}{ref} - 1)$, where $score$ is some performance metric of our algorithm (e.g. mean solution cost), and ref is a reference method performance metric (e.g. best-known solution so far). Similarly, the standard deviation σ of $score$ is also expressed relative to ref as $gap(\sigma) = 100\frac{\sigma}{ref}$.

A. TSP-SD experiments

The performance of the proposed GRASP solver for the TSP-SD is documented in Tab. II. The operators *swap* and *move* require parameters k, l, m . Their values were selected from ranges $k, l, m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ using the irace package [25]. The tuning resulted in the following setup: $m \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $(k, l) \in \{(1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 2), (2, 3), (3, 3)\}$. Thus, including 2-opt, the GRASP solver uses 9 different operators in all the following experiments.

The TSP-SD was originally formulated in [5] and solved with a generic metaheuristic solver [20]. This generic solver was tested on an artificial dataset of 11 instances, based on problems from the TSPLIB library [26], and the stop condition was given by a fixed computation time of $10|V|$ seconds, where $|V|$ is the number of nodes, indicated in each instance name. E.g., the instance eil101 has $|V| = 101$ nodes and thus was solved for 1010 seconds. The best-known solutions (BKS) from [5] are used as a reference here. The experimental setup is replicated, so the GRASP solver is tested with the same time budget of $10|V|$ seconds on the same machine. Each instance is solved 50 times. In Tab. II, we present gap values of $cost_{min}$ (best cost achieved over 50 runs), or $cost$ (average cost over 50 runs) relative to the BKS of the reference solver [5]. The TSP-SD is a minimization problem, so a negative gap means better than the BKS result.

The two smallest instances with 14 and 22 nodes were solved to optimality in each run. For the remaining 9 instances, the GRASP solver surpassed the BKS in 6 cases, both in the best and in the average performance. The BKS was not improved for three instances with up to 202 nodes, but the GRASP solver still found a solution within the 0.8% gap. As for the 5 largest instances (318 to 1084 nodes), the BKS were

TABLE I
TSP-CP RESULTS - DATASETS FROM [4]: HEXAGONS, MESHES; NEW DATASETS: NOISY HEXAGONS, SQUARES

reference solver [4]			proposed TSP-CP solver					reference solver [4]			proposed TSP-CP solver				
problem	BKS (-)	time (s)	r_{\max} (-)	gap values (%)			time (s)	problem	BKS (-)	time (s)	r_{\max} (-)	gap values (%)			time (s)
				r_{\max}	\bar{r} (σ)	\overline{cost}						r_{\max}	\bar{r} (σ)	\overline{cost}	
hex180	31.79	22	31.97	0.5	-0.7 (0.4)	0.2	111	mesh115	37.71	9	38.57	2.3	0.7 (0.7)	15.1	151
hex240	28.90	21	29.03	0.5	-0.2 (0.3)	0.9	124	mesh244	22.70	22	23.98	5.6	3.1 (1.4)	16.5	994
hex308	26.20	45	26.27	0.3	-0.4 (0.3)	1.0	281	mesh268	20.66	25	23.08	11.7	9.0 (1.9)	24.0	1996
hex336	24.63	52	24.56	-0.3	-0.7 (0.2)	0.4	316	mesh293	18.29	27	21.03	14.9	11.8 (1.5)	17.3	1727
hex416	22.50	49	22.50	0.0	-0.7 (0.3)	0.5	366	mesh343	18.58	41	20.30	9.3	5.5 (2.4)	25.3	3553
hex448	20.15	74	20.09	-0.3	-0.9 (0.3)	0.7	524	mesh374	18.64	31	19.28	3.4	1.3 (1.0)	19.7	4126
hex540	19.82	104	19.82	0.0	-0.6 (0.4)	0.0	473	mesh400	16.64	42	17.61	5.8	2.7 (1.9)	12.7	3175
hex576	18.24	69	18.15	-0.5	-0.8 (0.3)	0.0	295	mesh449	16.34	41	17.38	6.3	4.8 (1.0)	19.8	6431
hex836	15.52	134	15.58	0.4	-0.4 (0.5)	0.0	625	mesh686	11.89	70	13.56	14.0	10.1 (2.0)	18.9	22760
hex1144	13.39	227	13.39	0.0	-0.6 (0.4)	0.0	935	mesh1337	8.44	197	9.28	9.9	5.6 (1.9)	19.5	42390
average				0.1	-0.6 (0.3)	0.4		average				8.3	5.5 (1.6)	18.9	
hexN180	24.52	12	25.29	3.1	1.5 (0.9)	20.5	453	sqr117	23.68	11	24.93	5.3	1.6 (1.3)	9.9	133
hexN240	24.18	20	25.11	3.8	1.9 (1.1)	23.1	793	sqr225	21.86	22	22.64	3.6	1.7 (0.9)	16.4	743
hexN306	23.34	27	24.73	6.0	4.8 (0.8)	22.5	2148	sqr260	22.08	27	22.94	3.9	1.6 (1.2)	16.8	1564
hexN336	23.79	33	24.55	3.2	1.6 (1.1)	24.3	3209	sqr297	21.86	31	22.50	3.0	0.6 (1.1)	16.8	2186
hexN416	23.45	47	24.50	4.5	2.2 (1.7)	26.1	5929	sqr341	21.74	31	22.56	3.8	1.5 (1.0)	16.1	3093
hexN448	23.60	44	24.60	4.3	2.1 (1.6)	26.4	8503	sqr377	21.29	43	22.08	3.7	2.4 (1.0)	17.7	4843
hexN510	23.51	54	24.12	2.6	0.9 (1.3)	19.4	11991	sqr400	21.40	51	21.94	2.5	1.3 (0.7)	16.0	5469
hexN576	23.76	68	24.30	2.3	0.2 (1.3)	24.2	12357	sqr448	21.27	60	21.95	3.2	0.8 (0.9)	17.1	7047
hexN798	23.09	104	23.97	3.9	1.5 (1.6)	34.5	19531	sqr676	21.03	105	21.47	2.1	0.5 (0.8)	25.7	10864
hexN1056	22.80	154	23.65	3.7	1.8 (1.5)	38.9	28084	sqr1015	20.78	190	21.11	1.6	0.1 (0.7)	36.7	18130
average				3.7	1.8 (1.3)	26.0		average				3.3	1.2 (1.0)	18.9	

TABLE II
TSP-SD RESULTS (FIXED TIME OF $10|V|$ SEC.)

reference solver [5]		proposed GRASP solver			
problem	time budget (s)	BKS (-)	$cost_{\min}$ (-)	gap values (%)	
				$cost_{\min}$	\overline{cost} (σ)
burma14	140	52	52	0.0	0.0 (0.0)
ulysses22	220	141	141	0.0	0.0 (0.0)
berlin52-10	520	23866	24046	0.8	1.9 (0.7)
berlin52-13	520	17263	17287	0.1	5.7 (2.2)
eil101	1010	1394	1323	-5.1	-1.9 (2.5)
gr202	2020	812	814	0.3	2.5 (0.9)
lin318	3180	110698	100706	-9.0	-4.6 (1.4)
fl417	4170	27162	22807	-16.0	-5.4 (3.8)
d657	6570	85054	79925	-6.0	-3.3 (1.3)
rat783	7830	13753	12427	-9.6	-6.7 (1.0)
vm1084	10840	325218	295995	-9.0	-6.3 (1.7)
average				-4.9	-1.7 (1.4)

TABLE III
DTSP-CP RESULTS

problem- r_{dub}	r_{\max}	gap values (%)			time
	(-)	r_{\max}	\bar{r} (σ)	\overline{cost} (σ)	(s)
hex180-10	31.10	-2.7	-3.8 (0.5)	0.0 (0.0)	478
hex180-20	31.05	-2.9	-3.7 (0.8)	0.0 (0.0)	533
hex180-30	30.67	-4.1	-4.9 (0.6)	0.5 (2.3)	800
hexN180-10	24.59	-2.8	-4.7 (2.0)	2.1 (3.6)	1085
hexN180-20	24.58	-2.8	-5.0 (3.2)	0.0 (0.0)	1014
hexN180-30	24.31	-3.9	-14.0 (11.3)	21.1 (11.1)	1927
mesh115-10	37.76	-2.1	-5.5 (2.1)	9.4 (8.3)	803
mesh115-20	37.06	-3.9	-6.5 (2.7)	0.7 (2.2)	814
mesh115-30	36.94	-4.2	-6.5 (1.6)	0.0 (0.0)	906
sqr117-10	23.86	-4.3	-6.0 (1.2)	0.3 (1.3)	591
sqr117-20	24.44	-2.0	-5.5 (1.9)	0.0 (0.0)	299
sqr117-30	23.05	-7.5	-17.7 (12.6)	21.1 (11.2)	1434
average		-3.6	-7.0 (3.4)	4.6 (3.3)	

substantially improved by -9% to -16% . The \overline{cost} gaps range from -3.3% to -6.7% with an average standard deviation of 1.4% , which indicates that the new solver is not only capable

of improving the BKS, but robustly converges to better local optima on the large instances than the originally used generic solver.

B. TSP-CP experiments

The proposed TSP-CP solver is evaluated on four different datasets in Tab. I. The datasets in the top row (hexagons, meshes) are adopted from [4]. The nodes in the hexagons instances are placed on a regular hexagonal grid. The nodes in the mesh instances are randomly generated so that a certain minimal distance between them is maintained. The datasets in the bottom row (noisy hexagons, squares) are newly generated for this paper. The noisy hexagons instances are similar to the hexagons instances, but the node positions are randomly shifted, so the grid is not perfectly regular. Finally, the nodes in the square instances are placed on a regular square grid. As a reference, the Best-Known Solutions (BKS) generated using the bisection algorithm for the WPCCP from [4] are presented in both tables, together with \overline{time} (the average computation time). As the TSP-CP is a relaxation of the WPCCP, this experiment primarily documents the effect of the relaxation on the maximal radius of the placed circles. In Tab. I, we present the gap values of r_{\max} (best radius found by the proposed TSP-CP solver) and \bar{r} (average radius over 20 runs) relative to BKS (the largest radius found) of the reference WPCCP solver [4]. We also provide the gaps for the secondary objective \overline{cost} (average cost of the TSP-CP cycle) relative to $cost_{TSP}$ (optimal solution cost of the corresponding TSP instance). Note that $gap(r)$ is positive if r is better than BKS, but $gap(cost)$ better than reference would be negative. Each instance was solved 20 times.

Relaxing the WPCCP to the TSP-CP paid off most in the highly irregular meshes dataset, where the $gap(r_{\max})$ is 8.3% and in some mesh instances more than 10% . The effect is

lower in the noisy hexagons dataset (3.7%) and regular squares dataset (3.3%). Interestingly, the new formulation and solver did bring only a negligible benefit of 0.01% on the regular hexagons dataset. In the WPCCP, the circles are placed around a fixed TSP cycle of minimal cost, whereas in the TSP-CP, the cycle is allowed to change in order to create additional space for placing larger circles. The hexagonal structure appears to have some special property, which does not allow to take advantage of this TSP-CP feature. The average computation times of the proposed solver are up to two orders higher for those instances, that can be improved by the new formulation. This significant difference in computation requirements is caused by the fact that the reference solver is used as a subroutine [4] in the proposed solver. Thus, the reference solver on its own is not capable of achieving the same scores no matter the computation time. Regarding the cost of the TSP-CP solution, the gap from the optimal unconstrained TSP cycle $gap(\overline{cost})$ is often greater than 20%, except for the regular hexagons dataset. It appears that a higher radius of placed circles means a higher cost, which is an intuitive conclusion.

C. DTSP-CP experiments

The DTSP-CP solver is tested on a subset of four instances, one from each dataset and the results are presented in Tab. III. Each instance is solved with three different Dubins turning radii $r_{dub} \in \{10, 20, 30\}$. We provide the gap values of r_{max} and \bar{r} relative to r_{max}^{TSP-CP} (largest radius obtained by the proposed TSP-CP solver on a given instance, Tab. I). We also present gap of \overline{cost} relative to $cost_{DTSP}$ (cost of the corresponding Dubins TSP solution). The Dubins maneuvers are generated using the Dubins.jl library [27].

The average $gap(r_{max})$ over all instances and Dubins radii is -3.6% , suggesting that the Euclidean TSP-CP variant generally allows placing larger circles. The average $gap(\overline{cost})$ is relatively lower than in the Euclid variant, which corresponds to the lower $gap(\bar{r})$. In terms of computation times, the Dubins variant is around 4 to 8 times more expensive than the Euclid variant. There are two possible reasons for this. First, approximately $k^2|V|^2$ Dubins maneuvers must be calculated when solving the initial DTSP problem (line 1, Alg. 6). Second, each time a TSP-SD instance is generated (line 5, Alg. 5), all edges E in G must be checked for collisions with newly placed circles \mathcal{K} . Naturally, both of these operations are several times slower for the Dubins variant.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We present the Traveling Salesperson Problem with Circle Placement and its Dubins vehicle variant. Our contribution includes a novel heuristic solver for both variants, along with two solvers addressing related subproblems. We conduct a comparative analysis against state-of-the-art methods. In the future, we intend to modify the approach for placing circles of different radii aiming to maximize the area coverage. Furthermore, we aim for an extension to account for multiple vehicles as well as including different types of motions. We also intend to investigate the theoretical bounds on the radii of the placed circles.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Ullrich, J. Hertzberg, and S. Stiene, "Ros-based path planning and machine control for an autonomous sugar beet harvester," in *Proc. of Int. Conf. on Machine Control & Guidance (MCG-2014)*, 2014.
- [2] M. Mansouri, F. Lagriffoul, and F. Pecora, "Multi vehicle routing with nonholonomic constraints and dense dynamic obstacles," in *Int. Conf. on Intel. Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 3522–3529.
- [3] E. Salienko, "Mining drilling machine stock photo," <https://shorturl.at/pyDN0>, accessed: August 14, 2024.
- [4] M. Kulich, D. Woller, S. Carmesin, M. Mansouri, and L. Přeucil, "Where to place a pile?" in *European Conf. on Mobile Robots (ECMR)*, 2023, pp. 1–7.
- [5] S. Carmesin, D. Woller, D. Parker, M. Kulich, and M. Mansouri, "The hamiltonian cycle and travelling salesperson problems with traversal-dependent edge deletion," *J. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 74, p. 102156, 2023.
- [6] E. R. Collins and K. Stephenson, "A circle packing algorithm," *Comput. Geom.*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 233–256, 2003.
- [7] I. Castillo, F. J. Kampas, and J. D. Pintér, "Solving circle packing problems by global optimization: Numerical results and industrial applications," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 191, no. 3, pp. 786–802, 2008.
- [8] Y. Stoyan, A. Pankratov, and T. Romanova, *Placement Problems for Irregular Objects: Mathematical Modeling, Optimization and Applications*. Springer Int. Pub., 2017, pp. 521–559.
- [9] F. M. Iacopo Gentilini and K. Shimada, "The travelling salesman problem with neighbourhoods: Minlp solution," *Optim. Methods Softw.*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 364–378, 2013.
- [10] M. Kulich, J. Vidašič, and J. Mikula, "On the travelling salesman problem with neighborhoods in a polygonal world," in *Robotics in Natural Settings*. Springer Int. Pub., 2023, pp. 334–345.
- [11] D. J. Gulczynski, J. W. Heath, and C. C. Price, *The Close Enough Traveling Salesman Problem: A Discussion of Several Heuristics*. Springer US, 2006, pp. 271–283.
- [12] J. Deckerová, K. Kučerová, and J. Faigl, "On improvement heuristic to solutions of the close enough traveling salesman problem in environments with obstacles," in *European Conf. on Mobile Robots (ECMR)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [13] P. Váňa and J. Faigl, "On the dubins traveling salesman problem with neighborhoods," in *Int. Conf. on Intel. Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2015, pp. 4029–4034.
- [14] J. Faigl and R. Pěnička, "On close enough orienteering problem with dubins vehicle," in *Int. Conf. on Intel. Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2017, pp. 5646–5652.
- [15] O. Michail and P. G. Spirakis, "Traveling salesman problems in temporal graphs," *Theor. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 634, pp. 1–23, 2016.
- [16] S. Sharma and J. Chou, "Distributed and incremental travelling salesman algorithm on time-evolving graphs," *The Journal of Supercomputing*, vol. 77, no. 10, p. 10896–10920, Mar. 2021.
- [17] C.-S. Liao and Y. Huang, "The covering canadian traveller problem," *Theor. Comput. Sci.*, vol. 530, pp. 80–88, 2014.
- [18] A. Hellander and D. Axehill, "On a traveling salesman problem with dynamic obstacles and integrated motion planning," in *2022 American Control Conference (ACC)*, 2022, pp. 4965–4972.
- [19] M. G. Resende and C. C. Ribeiro, *Optimization by GRASP*. Springer New York, 2016.
- [20] D. Woller, J. Hrazdíra, and M. Kulich, "Metaheuristic solver for problems with permutative representation," in *Intel. Computing & Optimization*. Springer Int. Pub., 2022, pp. 42–54.
- [21] A. Duarte, J. Sánchez-Oro, N. Mladenović, and R. Todosijević, *Variable Neighborhood Descent*. Springer Int. Pub., 2018, pp. 341–367.
- [22] W. Cook, "Concorde tsp solver," <https://www.math.uwaterloo.ca/tsp/concorde.html>, 2020, accessed: August 14, 2024.
- [23] A. M. Shkel and V. Lumelsky, "Classification of the dubins set," *Robot. Auton. Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 179–202, 2001.
- [24] S. L. Smith and F. Imeson, "GLNS: An effective large neighborhood search heuristic for the generalized traveling salesman problem," *Comput. Oper. Res.*, vol. 87, pp. 1–19, 2017.
- [25] M. López-Ibáñez, J. Dubois-Lacoste, L. Pérez Cáceres, T. Stützle, and M. Birattari, "The irace package: Iterated racing for automatic algorithm configuration," *Oper. Res. Perspect.*, vol. 3, pp. 43–58, 2016.
- [26] G. Reinelt, "Tspplib—a traveling salesman problem library," *ORSA J. Comput.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 376–384, 1991.
- [27] K. Sundar, "Dubins.jl library," <https://docs.juliahub.com/Dubins/1ChBv/1.1.3/>, 2023, accessed: August 14, 2024.